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Abstract:

This milestone describes the final version of the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit, which was launched on April 20th, 2020 and updated throughout the rest of the SSHOC project. The Toolkit offers SSH trainers a way to discover and retrieve materials that can be used in training activities.

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Note on the terminology

Please note that while the original title of the toolkit mentioned in the grant proposal and agreement was “SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Toolkit” rather than “SSHOC Training Discovery Toolkit” (TDT), the name was adapted in the course of the project as it more accurately describes the content of the toolkit and its use. The TDT is directed at SSH trainers, but next to train-the-trainer materials, the TDT also contains information on other learning and training materials available for the SSH community. Moreover, the main purpose of the TDT is the discovery of these materials. Therefore, the name that is used in this milestone as well as in the deliverable is Training Discovery Toolkit. This is also what has been used on the SSHOC website and in the communications of the outcome.

1. Introduction

Task 6.4 of SSHOC Work Package 6 concerns the building of expertise within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) training community. One of the key outcomes of this task and the milestone described in this report is the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit (TDT). The TDT was developed to aid trainers in the SSH enabling them to discover materials that they can utilise in their own training activities. The TDT is a key resource for the SSH Training Community which is described in more detail in SSHOC *Deliverable 6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training Community*¹ as well as *Deliverable 6.13 Report on the SSHOC Training network (to be submitted at the same time as this milestone)*. The TDT was promoted and used during the SSHOC

¹ Ricarda Braukmann, & Ellen Leenarts. (2020). SSHOC D6.10 Report on the SSHOC Training Community (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558301> [accessed March 29th 2022].

Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps, which are described in more detail in *Deliverable 6.12 Report on Train-the-trainer Bootcamps*.²

2. Description of the Milestone

The TDT was launched on April 20th 2020³ and is since then accessible to the public at SSHOC official Website: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/>.

After the launch, the TDT has been promoted and updated to include more than 250 items relevant for trainers in the SSH. The initial development was described in *Deliverable 6.9 SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (draft)*⁴ and the performed updates are summarized below and described in more detail in *Deliverable 6.11 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (final) (to be submitted at the same time as this milestone)*.

The TDT was updated through consultation with the SSH Training community and presented and evaluated during the SSHOC Train-the-Trainer Bootcamps. New suggestions for materials were gathered and a curation sprint was held with the SSHOC T6.4 team to update the metadata information of existing records as well as to add new items and sources to the TDT. In addition to the extension of content, the user interface was updated and improved based on the feedback received from the community and during events. Moreover, the TDT metadata was evaluated against the criteria established by the focus group Minimal metadata for learning resources⁵ of the RDA Education and Training on handling of research data Interest Group⁶. This led to an adjustment of the data model and the metadata fields provided in the TDT to align with recommendations on minimum metadata for training materials. The controlled vocabularies were revised and extended. Where suitable already published controlled

² Darja Fišer, Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra, Judith Wehmeyer, Veronika Keck, Ellen Leenarts, Ricarda Braukmann, Tatsiana Yankelevich, & Cristina Magder. (2021). D6.12 Report on the SSHOC train-the-trainer bootcamps. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5734301> [accessed March 29th, 2022].

³ Link to the news item on the Toolkit <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-launches-toolkit-trainers-social-sciences-and-humanities> [accessed on 29th of April 2020].

⁴ Braukmann Ricarda, & Leenarts Ellen. (2020). SSHOC D6.9 SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (draft) (v1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4558299> [accessed March 29th, 2022].

⁵ More information about the Focus group is available at <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/education-and-training-handling-research-data-ig/wiki/ethrd-ig-focus-group-materials> [accessed on November 3rd, 2021].

⁶ More information about the RDA ETHRD IG is available at <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/education-and-training-handling-research-data.html> [accessed November 3rd, 2021].

vocabularies were integrated to improve the FAIRness and interoperability of the metadata. Last but not least, the TDT items were also mapped to schema.org to improve interoperability and facilitate indexing by search sites.

At the time of writing, the TDT lists over 240 materials from more than 95 different sources in various formats, such as modules, slides, games, videos and other items. A last curation sprint is planned for March 2022 where some more entries will be entered and the metadata will be reviewed and extended where possible. Materials in the TDT cover a range of topics including Research Data Management, FAIR data, text encoding, Open Science, and quantitative analysis, as well as didactics for better development and implementation of training activities. For a more detailed description of the content of the TDT please refer to *Deliverable 6.11 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (final) (to be submitted at the same time as this milestone)*.

2.1. Role of the Milestone

The TDT is an important resource for the SSH Training Community and one of the **key outputs of Work Package 6**. While there are many organisations that offer educational materials for trainers in the field of SSH, it has been challenging to find these materials. The Training Discovery Toolkit is meant to **provide a curated inventory** of these available materials allowing trainers to find them easily through one point of access. The TDT brings together information about the train-the-trainer materials developed and provided by the different SSHOC partners and research infrastructures (like CESSDA, CLARIN or DARIAH) as well as other relevant training nodes that the project has identified (like OpenAIRE or EOSC-Hub), and other sources that offer materials dedicated to trainers.

Since the launch, the TDT has been updated, now including more than double the number of entries that were available at launch. Improvements were carried out through the help of the SSH Training Community as well as by the continuous efforts of the SSHOC curation team. Moreover, since the launch at the beginning of 2020, the metadata quality was improved and metadata fields were evaluated to better conform with existing and developing standards for the documentation of training materials and learning resources.

There are plans to sustain the information gathered in the TDT after the end of the project. Initially the TDT will remain a separate service hosted by the Austrian Academy of Sciences / DARIAH and curated by the SSHOC consortium that plans to remain a collaborative network currently establishing a Memorandum of Understanding amongst the partners. In the longer term, there are plans to extend the metadata available in the SSH marketplace to cover metadata specific for learning resources which will

allow the TDT that already covers this metadata, to be merged into the SSH marketplace. A more detailed discussion of the TDT sustainability is available in *Deliverable 6.11 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (final)*⁷.

2.2. Means of verification

Since April 20th 2020 the TDT is available to the public on SSHOC official website: <https://training-toolkit.sshopencloud.eu/>. Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the main page of the Toolkit.

FIGURE 1: SCREENSHOT OF THE MAIN PAGE OF THE SSHOC TRAINING TOOLKIT

⁷ To be submitted at the same time as this milestone.

2.3. Explanation on delay in achieving the Milestone

There was an agreed change of the delivery date of this milestone and the related deliverable *D6.11 - SSHOC Trainer Toolkit (final)* from December 2021 to March 2022.

3. Conclusion

The Training Discovery Toolkit was successfully launched and updated through the work of the SSHOC Training team and in collaboration with the SSH Training Community. The TDT was promoted at various events where feedback and suggestions were gathered. The TDT was extended and improved in collaboration with the SSH Training Community as well as following guidelines and recommendations of the international community regarding training and education. While the SSHOC project is ending, the materials collected in the TDT will remain available through the TDT initially and merged into the marketplace eventually.